

Cluster Based Large Scale Demonstration and Yield Gap analysis of Food Barely Variety (HB-1307) in Hula District, Sidama Region, Ethiopia

*Wasihun Alemnew

Wondo genet agricultural research center, Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, Wondo Genet, Ethiopia

*Corresponding author: [Wasihun Alemnew](#)

Wondo genet agricultural research center, Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, Wondo Genet, Ethiopia

Email: wasihunmariam13@gmail.com

Abstract

The study was carried out in Ethiopia's Sidama region's Hula district. Purposefully, the district was chosen because of its potential for producing food barley. This paper's goal is to present the findings and experiences of cluster-based technology demonstrations about the technological and extension gaps of food barely variety. Two food barley producing kebeles were chosen from the district, and farmers were chosen based on their desire and the availability of land.

In the research regions, a single food variety (HB-1307) and its whole suggested packages were demonstrated through cluster farming approach. Field day was conducted with the participation of many stakeholders (Farmers, DAs, Experts, and Researchers) to showcase the food barley technology. Farmers found the variety (HB-1307) to be acceptable during field visits and field days because of its resistance to acidity in the soil, seed size and colour, plant biomass, grain yield, and early maturity productivity. Following harvest, the variety shown a good yield performance.

The overall harvested mean yield of HB-1307 and the local farmer practice was 3.8 tonha⁻¹ and 2.2 tonha⁻¹, respectively. Therefore, based on the results shown above HB1307 is the best performed variety in the study area.

Keywords: food barely, large scale demonstration, Hula district, gaps, farmer preference.

1. Introduction

After rice, wheat, and maize, barley is the fourth most important cereal crop in the world's top ten crops (Akar *et al.*, 2004 and Tilahun *et al.*, 2017). Ethiopia produces a substantial amount of barley in its highlands. Food barley is an emergency crop that may be planted to alleviate the severe food crisis because of its early maturity, claim Kemelew and Alemayehu (2011). Its grains are traditionally used to make local beers and "Injera" for eating at home and during festivities. These days, it undergoes a number of value-added procedures to produce a range of consumable food products, such as bread, soup, porridge, powder, and roasted grains.

There were several reasons for the crop's decreased output. According to Tadesse and Derso (2019), the primary ones are weed competition, poor crop management techniques, and a lack of proven improved varieties. Additionally, in barley growing agro-ecologies, the improved food barley technologies transfer activity is one choice for smallholder farmers who want to increase their output but do not have access to the desired improved variety seeds (Tadesse and Derso, 2019). The lack of better seed and the poor communication between the agriculture office and research made it extremely difficult for farmers to accept new technologies from research. To address the productivity issue in the study area, the country's national and regional research systems have been releasing a number of varieties and conducting a number of agricultural enhancement research projects.

Despite the fact that this variety is widely accessible, most farmers in the district still do not have access to it and instead employ recycled seed varieties, which are disreputable for their great vulnerability to disease and severely low yield. In the highlands of the Sidama region, particularly in the Hula district, food barley is mostly produced and consumed by smallholder farmers. Lack of improved seed varieties, inadequate application of production packages, and a high

incidence of rust diseases associated with both biotic and edaphic factors are the main causes of the region's low output yields. In the current barley production system in the area, farmers are more accustomed to using local varieties than they are to practice better complete production packages, including improved seed, agrochemicals, agronomic techniques, and other production inputs.

The six-rowed food type barley, HB 1307, was made available for usage in mid- and high-altitude areas by the Holetta Agricultural Research Centre in 2006. It was a hybrid of exotic germplasm (Awra gebs-1 x IBON93/91) and a land race line. Over a three-year period (2002–2004), tests showed its benefits in terms of stability, broad adaptation, and grain yield performance. It has good physical grain quality, moderate resistance to net and spot blotch, and resistance to lodging, leaf rust, and scald. It produces a significant quantity of biomass as well. Its variety, agronomic and qualitative qualities, and better performance than the checks make it dependable for similar agro-ecologies considered in the study. Therefore, this study was carried out to demonstrate and spread improved food barley technology at a cluster-based large-scale demonstration strategy by grouping farmers with full package application in order to increase production and productivity.

Objectives

1. To improve the production of improved food barley technology in the study area.
2. To identify the technology and extension gap of the study
3. To assess farmers' preferences about the improved food barley variety.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the study area

The study was conducted in the Sidama region of Ethiopia, specifically in the Hula area, over a period of two years. The district of Hula is part of the Sidama Regional Administration. The district is situated 93.4 kilometres southeast of Hawassa and 370 km south of Addis Ababa. The Highland agro-ecological zone makes up 72% of the district, while the remaining 28% is made up of the midland (HDAO 2021). The Hula district has a wet, cold temperate climate with an average annual temperature of 10 to 15°C and an annual rainfall of 1200 to 1800 mm. The most often grown crops in this district are cabbage (*Brassica carinata*), barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*), and enset (*Ensete ventricosum*) (SZPEDD, 2010). Hula is located close to the communities of Bursa and Dugo and is 2,653 meters above sea level elevation.

2.2 Site and farmer selection

Purposive sampling was used to choose the study region based on its potential for food barley production, suitability for diversity, and accessibility for supervision. Purposively, two excellent possible demonstration locations were selected from the district based on their potential for barley production and ease of access. 64 host farmers benefited from the demonstration, which involved the formation of four farmer research groups (FRG) units. In order to share experiences and learn about the diversity and production package of food, other farmers were set up as follower farmers under the host farmers. Development agents (DAs) and district agriculture specialists worked together to choose the sites and farmers. The farmers were chosen on the basis of their previous compatibility with cluster farming, their readiness to share advances with other farmers, their willingness to be held as cluster/farmer research members, and their accessibility for activity supervision. From each FRG unit, four model representative trial hosting farmers were selected, while the rest farmers were used as participant units.

Additionally, the experimenting farmers were selected based on a number of criteria, such as having sufficient land for the demonstration; being near roads to boost the possibility of other farmers visiting; having a history of successfully managing experimental plots or being committed to trust trials; and being forthright and honest when explaining the technology to others. Experts, DAs, and farmers were invited to a theoretical training session after the FRGs were established.

2.3 Activity implementation and field design

A multidisciplinary team of researchers from the Wondogenet Agricultural Research Centre (WgARC) trained sixty-four host farmers. Members of farmer research groups, development agents, and district specialists also received hands-on training in the following areas:

- Purpose and way of practice of FRG
- cluster farming approach
- Agronomic practices of food barely
- Post-harvest management and barley storage facilities.

The land was prepared for planting by properly plough it. On nearby areas, a minimum of 0.25ha of one food barley variety (HB-1307) was planted for each host farmer. Every plot received an equal application of all required recommended agronomic techniques. The rows of food barley were spaced 20 to 30 cm apart. The prepared rows are drilled with the suggested seed rate of 120 kg ha⁻¹. In the presence of sufficient soil moisture, a 5 cm depth of shallow planting was used. At the time of crop sowing or planting, the recommended fertilizer rate of NPS 100 kg ha⁻¹ was also applied. The demonstration sites were supervised periodically to assess the situation and find any gaps in order to facilitate collaborative monitoring and assessment. The experimental farmers, FRG members, follower farmers, WgARC researchers, and district agricultural specialists attended a participatory variety evaluation platform that was set up at the crop's maturity stage. The study's goals were implemented and met through the use of crucial implementation methods, such as ongoing field supervision, knowledge-sharing training, and the creation of training materials like pamphlets and field days.

2.4 Data collection and analysis

Both qualitative and quantitative data were gathered using appropriate techniques, such as focused group discussions and direct field observations and measurements. Descriptive statistics and ranking procedures were used to analyse the data and rate the variety attributes according to their significance.

2.5 Variety preference

According to Pena *et al.* (2002), growers produce cultivars that satisfy their end-use needs, are reliable in their area, and perform well under their particular management conditions. If a variety does not meet these criteria, a farmer is unlikely to accept it (Negatu and Parikh, 1999; Dahl *et al.*, 2001). Depending on the farmer's location, social status, end-use goals, gender, and other factors, the acceptability of a variety might vary significantly. Therefore, it is unlikely that all farmers will choose a single "super" variety (which would also be detrimental to plant breeders). It can take up to 15 or 20 years for a variant to become "widely adopted," therefore few ever do (Ceccarelli, 2012). This may be partly explained by a breeding process that ignores variety performance or usage adaptability in inadequate soil and management conditions, which are realities for most small-holder farmers.

2.6 Technology gap, extension gap and technology index

The extension gap is the difference between the demonstration yield and the yield of farmers' practices. To bridge the extension gap, we need to prepare and train partner farmers to apply the improved agricultural production technology. The inadequate adoption of new technology is indicated by larger extension gaps. The technology gap is the outcome of differences between demonstrated yield and prospective yield. The technological index, extension gaps, and technology gaps were computed using the methods used by Yadav *et al.* (2004).

Extension gap = Demonstration yield - Farmer yield

Technology gap = Potential yield - Demonstration yield

Technology index = $\frac{\text{Potential yield} - \text{Demonstration yield}}{\text{Potential yield}} \times 100$

2.7 Partial budget analyses

This section explains the formal logic of partial budget analysis using formulas and symbols. Even if some readers may find this treatment of the topic overly technical, it is necessary to cover the subject in order to guarantee that the technique is used appropriately. The following acronyms are used to facilitate the expression of economic concepts and relationships:

NI = net income

TR = total return

TC = total costs

FC = fixed costs

VC = variable costs = A change in any of the above, for example

Δ NI = change in net income,

R = rate of return

NI = TR - TC ----- (4.1)

Total returns (TR) correspond to the value of harvested yield.

Total costs (TC): include the costs of all inputs, such as seed, fertilizer, pesticides, labor and capital. For purposes of PBA, total costs can be separated into two groups: fixed costs (FC) and variable costs (VC):

$$TC = FC + VC \text{ ----- (4.2)}$$

When comparing a new technology to a farmer's current technology, fixed costs (FC) are the expenses that remain constant between the two. For instance, fertiliser, tillage, and weeding costs are the same in an experiment that tested various seed quality (as the example).

Note: Fixed costs (land) are not included in the cost of technology demonstration.

Conversely, variable costs (vc) are those that do differ among the technologies under consideration. The two technologies under evaluation—the seed cost and the capital cost—are the subject of the variable costs. When formulas 4.1 and 4.2 are combined, the following is produced:

$$NI = TR - (FC + VC) \text{ ----- (4.3)}$$

Change in net income (ANI). In deciding whether or not to adopt a new technology, a farmer wants to know if it will increase his net income. The increase of change in net income (ANI) is the difference between the change in total returns (ATR) and the change in fixed costs (AFC) and variable costs (AVC), according to formula 4.3:

$$ANI = ATR - (AFC + AVC). \text{ ----- (4.4)}$$

Fixed costs are, by definition, the same for both technologies: $AFC = 0$.

Thus formula 4.4 can be simplified to:

$$ANI = ATR - AVC. \text{ ----- (4.5)}$$

By application of a new technology a farmer expects an increase in net income.

Rate of return (R): In addition to change in net income, another criterion, the rate of return (R) is useful for evaluating the economics of adopting a new technology. R measures the increase in net income (ANI) which is generated by each additional unit of expenditure (AVC):

$$R = ANI/AVC \text{ ----- (4.6)}$$

To put it another way, R is the net return on extra capital spent on a new technology in comparison to the farmer's existing setup. If the new technology is less expensive than the farmer's existing technology, the rate of return (R) does not need to be calculated. If the alternative technology is more costly, the rate of return (R) must be higher than that of other possible investments and high enough to compensate for the risks associated with adoption. In general, we are not optimistic about the adoption of new technologies unless they have a minimum rate of return (R) of 1.0.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Training, field days, and experience sharing

A total of 325 people participated in district-wide extension activities, including 260 men and 65 women (Table 1). A wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, agricultural office specialists, and farmers (both host and non-host), were informed about the evaluation of large-scale demonstration plot field performance. Furthermore, a significant number of farmers came to the large scale demonstration plot to share their experiences with farmers from different localities. Better Barely technology products were used to reach a large audience through extension materials and mainstream media (television and radio). The adoption of technologies was accelerated by the farmers who were empowered through frequent training s, field trips to observe best practices, and experience sharing.

Table 1: Number of participants attended on extension events

Training participants (#325)	Extension Events			
	Training		Field day	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Farmers	82	18	105	24
Experts from office of agriculture	26	12	28	8
Researchers	5	-	14	3
Total	113	30	147	35

Source: own computation, 2022

3.2 Farmers variety traits preference

Strong preferences that represent their likes and dislikes are exhibited by the participants who benefit from improved farming technologies. Because of these preferences, they will swap out less wanted positive traits or attributes for more favoured ones. Interviewing the intended end users is therefore essential to ascertain the quality of a particular variety that they would want to have considered in plant breeding efforts. Because, in addition to being swiftly embraced, it will save time and resources when promoting and adopting the selected variety (Dan, 2012). The focus group discussion and preference evaluation during the crop green and maturity stage involved 42 stakeholders, of which 34 were farmers, 5 were agriculture specialists (DAs, supervisors), and 3 were researchers. Farmers' selection criteria were used to evaluate the variety when the crop reached at maturity stage.

The participants were first split up into small, manageable groups to aid in the evaluation and selection process; one group consisted of ten people, including a secretary and a group leader. At each demonstration site, the enumerators were given a brief orientation that covered how to arrange the data they had gathered, how to have a group discussion and reach a consensus, how to carefully evaluate each variety by considering each criterion and using a rating scale, and how to combine their criteria with the researchers' criteria to select the varieties that were demonstrated in order of importance. Lastly, the evaluators were told to submit their final report via their group leader.

Each variety was evaluated in relation to the criteria, which were grouped based on the relative importance of each trait. Following the process and debate (FGD) on the next steps, the assessors were shown the evaluation's outcome. Accordingly, the chosen variety will be suggested for additional scaling up.

Table 2: FRG member preferences and ranking towards the demonstrated barley variety

N o	Food barley variety	Selection criteria						Rank
		GSC	B	DR	GY	EM	Overall	
1	HB-1307	5	5	4	4	4	22	1 st
2	(EH-1493) Locally recycled Variety	3	2	2	3	4	14	2 nd

GSC = Grain size and color, B = Biomass, DR = Disease resistance, GY = Grain Yield, EM = Early maturity; **Scores:** - 1= Very poor 2= Poor 3 = Good 4 = Very good 5 = Excellent

Another crucial component of this study is the farmers' participatory assessment of the variety attributes. As a result, farmers assessed technology using their own standards and demonstrated how they choose a variety for their areas. Farmers, researchers, and agricultural specialists were among the several stakeholders who took part in the participatory evaluation and selection process. 42 people in all participated in the maturity stage of the selection process. Farmers were helped to create their own selection criteria during the assessment, which could help them find the best variety to meet their needs. Tillering ability, resistance to disease and pests, early maturity, seed size, resistance to lodging, and seed colour are some of these characteristics. Accordingly, farmer's ranked disease and pest tolerance trait and seed size and seed color also ranked 2nd and 3rd respectively (table-3). Therefore, based on objectively measured traits and farmers preferences; breeders focus on the traits of disease and pest tolerance, seed size and color at the time of breeding process.

Table-3: Pair wise ranking result to rank variety traits in order of importance

N.O	Traits	A	B	C	D	E	F	Score	rank
1	Disease and pest tolerance (A)		A	A	A	A	A	5	1
2	Seed size (B)			B	B	B	B	4	2
3	Seed color (C)				C	C	C	3	3
4	Tillering capacity (D)					D	D	2	4
5	Lodging (E)						E	1	5
6	Early maturity (F)							0	6

3.3 On-farm performance of food barley variety

The yield performance of the HB-1307 variety was encouraging even though there would inevitably be differences in performance between the farmer practices and the presented methods. The locally recycled cultivar produced 22 qt ha-1, while HB-1307 produced an overall harvested mean yield of 38 qt ha-1. Thus, compared to the farmer's practice, the

yield advantage of the HB-1307 food barely variety is 72.72%. In contrast to farmer practices, this might be the result of employing better entire production packages that include better seed, pesticides, the proper time to sow, seed treatment, row planting, weed control, and periodic technical supervision.

$$\text{Yield advantage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Demonstrated variety Yield} - \text{Local check variety Yield}}{\text{Local check Yield}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Yield advantage \% for HB-1307} = \frac{38\text{qt/ha} - 22\text{qt/ha}}{22\text{qt/ha}} \times 100 = 72.72 \%$$

Therefore, HB 1307 has 72.72 % yield advantage over the EH-1493 locally recycled variety

3.4 Technology Gap, Extension gap, and technology index

The technology gap, extension gap and technology index were computed by using the following formulae

1. Technology gap = Potential yield- Demonstrations yield.
2. Extension gap = Demonstrations Yield-Farmers practice yield.
3. Technology Index = $\frac{\text{Potential Yield} - \text{Demonstration Yield}}{\text{Potential Yield}} \times 100$

Extension gap: A total of 325 people participated in district-wide extension activities, including 260 men and 65 women (Table 1). A wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, agricultural office specialists, and farmers (both host and non-host), were informed about the evaluation of large-scale demonstration plot field performance. Furthermore, a significant number of farmers came to the large demonstration plot to share their experiences with farmers from different localities. To reach a large audience with improved Barely technology packages, extension materials and mass media (internet, radio, and television) were used.

Technology gap and its index: The difference between the prospective yields of the variety attained during on-farm demonstrations on farmers' fields and those obtained on-station under the breeder's supervision was undoubtedly caused by a number of factors. Variations in the fertility of the soil, the unpredictability of larger plots, follow-up and less frequent inspection of the on-farm study, and weather variations were some of the factors that contributed to this disparity. A crop type's greater adaptability was represented by a smaller technical divide.

The observed technology gap and technology index of the food barley variety (BH-1307) under inquiry were calculated using the aforementioned formulae. Table 4 below displays the results. According to the previously provided data, the mean technology index for BH-1307 is 24%.

Comparing the food barley variety BH-1307 to the farmer's practice of 12 qt/ha during the presentation, the mean yield gap yield performance is similar. The technology index (24%) in Table 1 illustrates how practical it is for farmers to employ developing technology in their fields. The lower the technology index value, the more technologically possible something is. This proves that growing the food barley variety (HB-1307) in the study area is feasible. Greater technological feasibility was indicated by the technology index's highest value. It demonstrates the effectiveness of well-executed pertinent interventions or technologies in the field of farmers.

Table-4: BH-1307 barley variety yield, technology gap, and technology index in Hula district

Variety	Yield (Qt/ha)				Technology Gap	Extension Gap	Technology index (%)
	Potential	Demonstration	Farmer practice	Yield advantage (%)			
HB-1307	50	38	22	72.72	12	16	24

Table-5: Cost-benefit analysis summary for food barely technology demonstration

N.O	Items	Demonstration	Local practice
1	Gross benefit (A+B)	139,000	81,500
A	Grain yield (ETB/ha)	133,000	77,000
B	Biomass yield	6,000	4,500
2	Variable cost (C+D+E+F)	58,300	30,600
C	Seed cost (ETB/ha)	7,200	10,800
D	Fertilizer cost (ETB/ha)	17,700	11,800
E	Chemical cost (ETB)	8,400	1,500
F	Cost of labor (ETB/ha)	25,000	6,500

3	Net benefit (ETB) (1-2)	80,700	50,900
4	Rate of return (3/2)	2.4	1.6

Source: own data computation, 2020

3.6 Lessons Learned

Extensive on-farm demonstrations facilitate mutually beneficial knowledge sharing between farmers and researchers. Farmers were able to observe HB-1307's real performance throughout the study. The study team was given feedback for further studies and put through a collective variety evaluation in an effort to boost the food's production and productivity. The study team's relationships with experts, DAs, farmers, and other stakeholders were strengthened in order to transfer the ideas. Farmers gained more expertise and understanding in managing barley crops. They were also provided improved barley cultivars that fit their particular ecological, cultural, and economical conditions.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The evaluators found that seed size and colour, disease resistance, biomass, and grain yield were the most frequently employed selection criteria in the area for selecting the best-performing variety or kinds. The HB-1307 food barley variety demonstrated promising yield performance, despite the fact that farmers' methods will always differ in performance.

Smallholder farmers receive technical assistance and guidance to boost barley yield and achieve the desired results. These days, the smallest association of farmers is believed to be farmers' groups. Therefore, one of the extension strategies that places the farmer at the centre of agricultural research, technology promotion, and dissemination is the creation and strengthening of FRGs/FREGs.

The HB 1307 variety was chosen, and in order to increase popularity, it was recommended that they pre-scale up operations on a larger plot (at least 0.5 hectares per trial farmer). To accomplish the goal, stakeholder relationships must be improved. This extension gap tendency will eventually be reversed by the widespread use of the most modern production techniques in conjunction with improved high-yielding varieties. The introduction of modern technologies allows farmers to give up their traditions.

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